

DEVELOPMENT OF VIDEO SONG-BASED LEARNING MEDIA ON ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILLS PHASE E STUDENTS AT SMAN 1 PULAU PUNJUNG

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Abstract

This research aimed to see the extent to which students are interested in learning using song videos. The development of song-video-based learning can provide more understanding, insight, and knowledge to students, especially students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung so that students can improve their abilities. Skills their English more actively. This research method was carried out using a non-quantitative method associative. The research sample numbered 73 people from 268 phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung. Based on the needs analysis questionnaire distributed, it can be concluded that the development of song-video-based learning media was indeed very important and needed following the interest indicator of 94% in the very high category and the need indicator of 92% in the also very high category.

Keywords: videos, songs, instructional media, speaking skills

INTRODUCTION

English is an international language that is important in global communication, business, education, and many aspects of modern life. In learning English, there are 4 skill competencies that must be mastered, namely reading, writing, listening, and speaking (Irawan & Surjono, 2018; Tsai, 2023; Rusmiyanto et al., 2023; Suoth et al., 2023; Wahyuni et al., 2023). Efforts to instill English in the younger generation are not easy, therefore teachers play an important and very large role in the process.

Improving the speaking ability in English is the main goal of learning English. Good speaking skills enable a person to communicate effectively in a variety of situations, open doors to educational and career opportunities, and enrich the experience of social interactions (Ban et al., 2023; Alaon et al., 2023; Herlisya & Wiratno, 2022; Shofi, 2020; Lingga et al., 2020; Meinawati et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2017).

English is the dominant or official language in a large number of fields, such as diplomacy, science, aviation, entertainment, and internet. English is used in all fields. Whatever our work will be, it will not be separated from English. There will come a time when English is not just an advantage, but a basic requirement. This shows how important English is in modern life (Bolton & Graddol, 2012; Ilyosovna, 2020; Rao, 2019; Suryasa et al., 2017; DeWilde et al., 2020; Smith, 2015; Choi, 2021). Where a large number of fields use English as the main language.

A country that has mastered English can be concluded that the country has entered the era of globalization. Countries that master English can easily establish international relations with other countries, therefore many countries are competing to teach English to their people. As early as possible to survive and be able to compete well in the global world (Kasdi & Wijayanti, 2017). As important as it is to improve

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students' English speaking skills, this is a challenge for most students, especially those who have a different mother tongue. Speaking skills require understanding grammar, vocabulary, intonation, and appropriate expressions (Derakhshan et al., 2016; Shobikah, 2020; Bohari, 2020). Many students today are not able to master English well. It caused the way of teacher teaching practice. Some teachers still tend to rely on the lecture method which has the potential to make students feel bored and less involved in the learning process (Hermanto et al., 2021; Lesmana et al., 2019; Fathoni et al., 2017; Fajri & Sahlan, 2023).

Teachers often face challenges in motivating students to speak more in English. The sample that the researchers observed were phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung. The problem faced is the lack of motivation of students to speak English. Students are reluctant and even tend not to want to speak English. They are more passive when asked to actively speak English. Researchers also often find fear and lack of confidence in pronouncing sentences and even words in English. Apart from that, the lack of vocabulary is also another reason that researchers found.

Under current developments, where technological developments are increasingly high, including access to digital media which is used to change the way students interact with information and media. Encouragement from the development of information and communication technology encourages teachers to produce technology-based learning media, with the aim of improving the overall quality of education (Mulyani & Haliza, 2021).

Changes in learning models and methods applied by teachers in the context of online learning have a positive impact on learning success (Dong et al., 2020; Syaifullah et al., 2024; Novianto & Nadawina, 2022; Sholihah et al., 2023; Lesmana & Arpan, 2017). Education requires learning media that makes students able to acquire knowledge, skills, or attitudes (Feladi et al., 2017; Putri et al., 2022; Sulistiyarini et al., 2018; Hernando et al., 2022; Ananda & Rakhmawati, 2022; Batubara, 2023).

Learning media that is applied effectively supports the success of educators in getting students to understand a problem through all

stages of the process learning is carried out by the objectives set (Dewi 2018; Kusnasari & Rakhmawati, 2022; Muna et al., 2023). Learning media has also experienced significant changes in line with developments over time. The first thing teachers must pay attention to is creating relaxed learning activities, as well as delivering material that is interesting and not boring (Sofa et al., 2023; Sii et al., 2017; Supardi et al., 2023).

The use of song-video media in English language learning has received attention because of its potential to improve students' speaking skills. Songs are a colorful and vibrant vehicle that can stimulate imagination, emotion, and interaction (Storr, 2015; Natalie, 2016; Tan et al., 2017; Adolphe, 2021). The song lyrics also introduce English vocabulary and intonation in an interesting and easy-to-remember way (Akbar et al., 2016; Phisutthangkoon, 2016; Hendrawaty, 2019; Halawa, 2021; Rachmawati et al., 2020). Therefore, this research will explain how the use of song media is considered a potential solution for improving student's English speaking skills.

Some of research results shown that the use of songs in language learning can increase student motivation, strengthen speaking skills, and introduce rich cultural elements of the language (Mangelen et al., 2023; Engh, 2013; Pinter, 2017). Intrinsic motivation theory, communicative approach, and cultural understanding are relevant frameworks in supporting the use of song media in English language learning (Shabani & Alipoor, 2017; Hassan et al., 2020; Green & Fujita, 2016; Khan et al., 2021; Lai, 2013). Apart from that, the use of song-video media is also by learning methods that are adapted to the age of the students (Rahman et al., 2018; Ardianto et al., 2021).

Students tend to be more motivated to learn when they feel they have control and autonomy in the learning process. This theory explains that intrinsic motivation arises when individuals feel that the activity is meaningful, allows autonomy, and provides satisfaction. The use of song media in learning English can increase students' intrinsic motivation because songs are often associated with positive and pleasant emotions. Students feel more motivated to speak English when they enjoy the activity and feel they have control over the choice of songs they like.

Teachers who are creative in introducing

English make it easier for many children to understand English because of the teacher's maximum understanding of models, methods, and media (Purwanti & Suhaimi, 2020). The use of song-video media is one method that can make it easier for students to understand the material presented, and it also makes a big contribution to students' quick understanding. By using song videos, students indirectly increase the vocabulary of the song.

Singing is also a fun activity that can train children's motor skills so that children can be motivated to listen, learn, and repeat what they indirectly learn from the song (Uzer, 2019). The use of song-video media in English language learning can enable students to feel more involved and have freedom in choosing the songs they like. This can help increase students' motivation to speak English, as they feel more involved in the learning process through a media they enjoy. So, this research aimed to develop song video-based learning media for phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung.

METHOD

This research method was carried out using a non-quantitative method associative. The research sample numbered 73 people from 268 phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung. This research was based on the results of a needs analysis. The focus of this research was on how to make students have English speaking skills through learning media based on song videos.

Data collection technique was carried out by distributing questionnaires or answering several questions in the needs analysis for phase E students at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung. In this research, a direct questionnaire was used with closed questions, namely with answers to the questions asked and available.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial observations show that the majority of students find it difficult to develop skills in speaking English. The findings in this research show that the majority of students prefer to learn through video-based media and almost all of them have access to video playing devices. This indicates a match between student preferences and the proposed learning method. They show high interest in aspect-oriented

learning methods audio visual, especially the use of song videos.

Songs can be used as learning tools for very good reasons. Not only can songs be enjoyed while learning, they can also be used to teach many language skills and linguistic features including vocabulary, sentences, pronunciation, intonation, and grammar. Reading, writing, speaking, and listening, everything can be taught holistically and together.

Songs help children relax and be motivated, which makes it easy for them to remember the language they have learned (Brewster et al., 2007; Murphey, 1993) and songs may be remembered in the mind for a long time (Ratminingsih & Budasi, 2014; Arthur, 2023; Werner, 2018). As a learning media, song videos are effective for use as mass learning, individual or group (Daryanto, 2012).

Teachers must be able to create a learning environment in normal classroom activities that is interesting and enjoyable so that students feel they can make it an enjoyable experience. From analysis data need and interested can get that students show a fairly high level of interest in learning English through song videos. It can be seen from the result of answering the question that is given at the written question in need analysis and interested. These findings may reflect that video-based learning media can be an effective means of arousing students' interest in speaking skills.

At the initial needs analysis stage, the research results identified concrete difficulties faced by students in developing English speaking skills. Such as, difficulty in understanding intonation, pronunciation, or relevant vocabulary. Researchers highlight how to use and select song media with clear lyrics and be equipped with visual images that can help students understand and express concepts that may be difficult in English speaking skills.

Many things make students unable to develop their English speaking skills. These things are caused by students' lack of motivation to learn, lack of self-confidence, and also minimal vocabulary. Based on the problem above, the researcher obtained observation results from a needs analysis questionnaire distributed to students which contained two questions, namely interest in video-based learning media and need for video-based learning

media. The questions asked were related to how high their level of interest and need was for this song video-based learning.

This needs analysis was researched based on the number of samples and population at SMA N 1 Pulau Punjung. This can be seen based on the following data.

Table 1. Population Number of Research and Development of Song Video-Based Learning Media for Phase E Students of SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung Academic Year 2023/2024

Class	Number of Students
Phase E1	35 people
Phase E2	34 people
Phase E3	35 people
Phase E4	34 people
Phase E5	33 people
Phase E6	34 people
Phase E7	34 people
Phase E8	29 people
Summary	268 people

Table 1 explains the population from which the research sample will be taken. Of the 268 populations to be studied, 73 were obtained sample by using Taro Yamane's formula is as follows.

$$n = \frac{N}{N \cdot d^2 + 1} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

n = Sample size
 N = Population size
 d = Percentage of error allowance due to sampling (10 %)

So the sample is obtained as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{N \cdot d^2 + 1}$$

$$n = \frac{268}{268 \cdot 0,1^2 + 1}$$

$$n = \frac{268}{268,01 + 1}$$

$$n = \frac{268}{2,68 + 1}$$

$$n = \frac{268}{3,68}$$

$$n = 72,82 = 73$$

The data obtained will be analyzed based on a range of values with scoring as follows: 90-100 Very high, 89-80 High, 79-65 Medium, 64-55 Low, 54-0 Very low. Through a needs analysis questionnaire consisting of two variables regarding students' interests and needs regarding the need for song video-based

learning media, showed that almost all students expressed interest and need for song video-based learning media. From 73 correspondents answered interesting. It created the results are as follows.

Figure 1. Analysis of Data Requirements in the Development of Learning Media Based on Video Song on English Speaking Skills Material

Based on Figure 1, 12 questions were given to students. Almost all students expressed interest and need for song video-based learning media. In the interest variable, it can be seen that students' interest is very high in video-based learning media. Likewise with the needs variable. It can be seen that students' need for fun learning media such as song videos is very high. This showed that there has been learning so far studied it feels uninteresting for students.

Based on the needs analysis questionnaire distributed, it can be concluded that the development of song video-based learning media is indeed very important needed in accordance with the interest indicator of 94% in the very high category and the need indicator of 92% in the also very high category.

Based on the results of the data above can be concluded that research based on an analysis of the needs for developing song video-based learning media received a positive response positive from the students. They felt very interested and also felt the need for this song-video-based learning media.

CONCLUSION

Learning videos are a type of media that has audio (sound) and visual motion (moving images) elements. As a learning medium, videos act as an introduction to information from teachers to students. The ease of repeating videos (replay) and the way of presenting information in a structured manner makes video one of the media that can improve students' ability to understand a concept. Several of the advantages that have been described prove that video is a medium that has many positive values and is effective for use in the learning process, especially for elementary school students. However, video selection must also be considered customized with learning objectives, learning materials, learning methods, facilities, and infrastructure.

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